

Approximation of Fourier Series of a function of Lipchitz class by Product Means

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Abstract: Lipchitz class of function had been introduced by McFadden [8]. Recently dealing with degree of approximation of Fourier series of a function of Lipchitz class Nigam [12] and Misra et al.[9,10,11] have established certain theorems. Extending their results, in this paper a theorem on degree of approximation of a function $f \in W(L^p, \xi(t))$ by product summability $(E, s)(N, p_n, q_n)$ has been established.

Keywords: Degree of Approximation; $W(L^p, \xi(t))$ class of function; $(E, s)(N, p_n, q_n)$ product mea; Fourier series; Lebesgue integral.

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1. Introduction:

Let $\sum a_n$ be a given infinite series with sequence of partial sums $\{s_n\}$. Let $\{p_n\}$ and $\{q_n\}$ be sequences of positive real numbers such that

$$(1.1) \quad P_n = \sum_{\nu=0}^n p_\nu \quad \text{and} \quad Q_n = \sum_{\nu=0}^n q_\nu .$$

Let

$$(1.2) \quad t_n = \frac{1}{r_n} \sum_{\nu=0}^n p_{n-\nu} q_\nu s_\nu ,$$

where $r_n = p_0 q_n + p_1 q_{n-1} + \dots + p_n q_0 (\neq 0)$, $p_{-1} = q_{-1} = r_{-1} = 0$.

Then $\{t_n\}$ is called the sequence of (N, p_n, q_n) mean of the sequence $\{s_n\}$. If

$$(1.3) \quad t_n \rightarrow s \quad , \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty ,$$

then the series $\sum a_n$ is said to be (N, p_n, q_n) summable to s .

The necessary and sufficient conditions for regularity of (N, p_n, q_n) method are[3]:

$$(1.4) \quad (i) \frac{p_{n-\nu}q_\nu}{r_n} \rightarrow 0, \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty, \text{ for each integer } \nu \geq 0$$

and

$$(1.5) \quad (ii) \sum_{\nu=0}^n |p_{n-\nu}q_\nu| < H|r_n| ,$$

where H is a positive number independent of n .

The sequence –to–sequence transformation [5],

$$(1.6) \quad T_n = \frac{1}{(1+q)^n} \sum_{\nu=0}^n \binom{n}{\nu} q^{n-\nu} s_\nu ,$$

defines the sequence $\{T_n\}$ of the (E, q) mean of the sequence $\{s_n\}$. If

$$(1.7) \quad T_n \rightarrow s , \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty ,$$

then the series $\sum a_n$ is said to be (E, q) summable to s . Clearly (E, q) method is regular [5].

Further, the (E, q) transform of the (N, p_n, q_n) transform of $\{s_n\}$ is defined by

$$(1.8) \quad \begin{aligned} \tau_n &= \frac{1}{(1+q)^n} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} q^{n-k} t_k \\ &= \frac{1}{(1+q)^n} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} q^{n-k} \left\{ \frac{1}{r_k} \sum_{\nu=0}^k p_{k-\nu}q_\nu s_\nu \right\} \end{aligned}$$

If

$$(1.9) \quad \tau_n \rightarrow s , \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty ,$$

then $\sum a_n$ is said to be $(E, q)(N, p_n, q_n)$ - summable to s .

Let $f(t)$ be a periodic function with period 2π and L- integrable over $(-\pi, \pi)$, The Fourier series associated with f at any point x is defined by

$$(1.10) \quad f(x) \sim \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n \cos nx + b_n \sin nx) \equiv \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_n(x).$$

The L_∞ - norm of a function $f : R \rightarrow R$ is defined by

$$(1.11) \quad \|f\|_\infty = \sup \{ |f(x)| : x \in R \}$$

and the L_ν - norm is defined by

$$(1.12) \quad \|f\|_\nu = \left(\int_0^{2\pi} |f(x)|^\nu dx \right)^{\frac{1}{\nu}}, \quad \nu \geq 1.$$

The degree of approximation of a function $f : R \rightarrow R$ by a trigonometric polynomial $P_n(x)$ of degree n under norm $\|\cdot\|_\infty$ is defined by

$$(1.13) \quad \|P_n - f\|_\infty = \sup \{ |P_n(x) - f(x)| : x \in R \}$$

and the degree of approximation $E_n(f)$ of a function $f \in L_\nu$ is given by [17]

$$(1.14) \quad E_n(f) = \min_{P_n} \|P_n - f\|_\nu.$$

This method of approximation is called Trigonometric Fourier approximation.

A function $f \in Lip\alpha$ if [8]

$$(1.15) \quad |f(x+t) - f(x)| = O(|t|^\alpha), \quad 0 < \alpha \leq 1,$$

and $f \in Lip(\alpha, r)$, for $0 \leq x \leq 2\pi$, if [8]

$$(1.16) \quad \left(\int_0^{2\pi} |f(x+t) - f(x)|^r dx \right)^{\frac{1}{r}} = O(|t|^\alpha), \quad 0 < \alpha \leq 1, \quad r \geq 1, \quad t > 0.$$

For a positive increasing function $\xi(t)$ and an integer $r > 1$, $f \in Lip(\xi(t), r)$ if [15]

$$(1.17) \quad \left(\int_0^{2\pi} |f(x+t) - f(x)|^r dx \right)^{\frac{1}{r}} = O(\xi(t)).$$

For a given positive increasing function $\xi(t)$ and an integer $p > 1$ the function $f(x) \in W(L^p, \xi(t))$, if [7]

$$(1.18) \quad \left(\int_0^{2\pi} |f(x+t) - f(x)|^p (\sin x)^{p\beta} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} = O(\xi(t)), \quad \beta \geq 0.$$

We use the following notation throughout this paper:

$$(1.19) \quad \phi(t) = f(x+t) + f(x-t) - 2f(x),$$

$$(1.20) \quad s_n(f; x) : \text{nth partial sum of the Fourier series given by (1.10)}$$

and

$$(1.21) \quad K_n(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi(1+s)^n} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} s^{n-k} \left\{ \frac{1}{r_k} \sum_{\nu=0}^k p_{k-\nu} q_\nu \frac{\sin\left(\nu + \frac{1}{2}\right)t}{\sin \frac{t}{2}} \right\}.$$

Further, the method $(E, q)(N, p_n, q_n)$ is assumed to be regular and this case is supposed throughout the paper.

2. Known Theorems:

Bernstein[2], Alexits[1], Sahney and Goel [13], Chandra [4] and several others have determined the degree of approximation of the Fourier series of the function $f \in Lip\alpha$ by $(C,1)$, (C,δ) , (N, p_n) and $(\bar{N}, p_n)$ means. Subsequently, working on the same direction Sahney and Rao[14], and Khan[6] have established results on the degree of approximation of the function belonging to the class $Lip\alpha$ and $Lip(\alpha, r)$ by (N, p_n) and (N, p_n, q_n) means respectively. However, dealing with product summability Nigam et al [12] proved the following theorem on the degree of approximation by the product $(E, q)(C,1)$ - mean of Fourier series.

Theorem 2.1:

If a function f is 2π - periodic and of class $Lip\alpha$, then its degree of approximation by $(E, q)(C,1)$ summability mean on its Fourier series $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_n(t)$ is given by $\|E_n^q C_n^1 - f\|_{\infty} = O\left(\frac{1}{(n+1)^{\alpha}}\right)$, $0 < \alpha < 1$, where $E_n^q C_n^1$ represents the (E, q) transform of $(C,1)$ transform of $s_n(f; x)$.

Subsequently Misra et al [9] have established the following theorem on degree of approximation by the product mean $(E, q)(N, p_n)$ of the Fourier series:

Theorem 2.2:

If f is a 2π - Periodic function of class $Lip(\alpha, r)$, then degree of approximation by the product $(E, q)(N, p_n)$ summability means on its Fourier series (defined above) is given by $\|\tau_n - f\|_{\infty} = O\left(\frac{1}{(n+1)^{\alpha-\frac{1}{r}}}\right)$, $0 < \alpha < 1$, $r \geq 1$, where τ_n as defined in (1.8).

Further, Misra et al [10] have established the following theorem on degree of approximation by the product mean $(E, s)(N, p_n, q_n)$ of the Fourier series:

Theorem 2.3:

If f is a 2π - Periodic function of the class $Lip(\alpha, l)$, then degree of approximation by the product $(E, s)(N, p_n, q_n)$ summability means on its Fourier series (1.10) is given by $\|\tau_n - f\|_{\infty} = O\left(\frac{1}{(n+1)^{\alpha-\frac{1}{l}}}\right)$, $0 < \alpha < 1$, $l \geq 1$, where τ_n is as defined in (1.8).

Recently, Misra et al [11] proved the following Theorem

Theorem -2.4 :

For a positive increasing function $\xi(t)$ and an integer $l > 1$, if f is a 2π - Periodic function of the class $Lip(\xi(t), l)$, then degree of approximation by the product $(E, s)(N, p_n, q_n)$ summability on its Fourier series (1.10) is given by $\|\tau_n - f\|_{\infty} = O\left((n+1)^{\frac{1}{l}} \xi\left(\frac{1}{n+1}\right)\right)$, $l \geq 1$, where τ_n is as defined in (1.8).

In this paper, we have established a theorem on degree of approximation by the product mean $(E, s)(N, p_n, q_n)$ of the Fourier series of a function of class $W(L^p, \xi(t))$. We prove:

3. Main Theorem

Let $\xi(t)$ be a positive increasing function and f a 2π -Periodic function of the class $W(L^p, \xi(t))$, $p > 1, t > 0$. Then degree of approximation by the product $(E, s)(N, p_n, q_n)$ summability means on the conjugate series (1.10) of the Fourier series (1.9) is given by

$$(3.1.1) \quad \|\tau_n - f\|_r = O\left((n+1)^{\beta+\frac{1}{l}} \xi\left(\frac{1}{n+1}\right)\right), l \geq 1,$$

provided

$$(3.1.2) \quad \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{n+1}} \left(\frac{t \phi(t) \sin^\beta t}{\xi(t)}\right)^l dt\right)^{\frac{1}{l}} = O\left(\frac{1}{n+1}\right)$$

and

$$(3.1.3) \quad \left(\int_{\frac{1}{n+1}}^{\pi} \left(\frac{t^{-\delta} |\phi(t)|}{\xi(t)}\right)^l dt\right)^{\frac{1}{l}} = O\left((n+1)^\delta\right)$$

hold uniformly in x , where δ is an arbitrary number such that $m(1-\delta)-1 > 0$ and τ_n is as defined in (1.7).

4. Required Lemmas:

We require the following Lemmas for the proof the theorem.

Lemma -4.1:

$$|K_n(t)| = O(n), \quad 0 \leq t \leq \frac{1}{n+1}.$$

Proof of Lemma-4.1:

For $0 \leq t \leq \frac{1}{n+1}$, we have $\sin nt \leq n \sin t$.

then

$$\begin{aligned} |K_n(t)| &= \frac{1}{2\pi(1+s)^n} \left| \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} s^{n-k} \left\{ \frac{1}{r_k} \sum_{\nu=0}^k p_{k-\nu} q_\nu \frac{\sin\left(\nu + \frac{1}{2}\right)t}{\sin \frac{t}{2}} \right\} \right| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2\pi(1+s)^n} \left| \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} s^{n-k} \left\{ \frac{1}{r_k} \sum_{\nu=0}^k p_{k-\nu} q_\nu \frac{(2\nu+1)\sin \frac{t}{2}}{\sin \frac{t}{2}} \right\} \right| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2\pi(1+s)^n} \left| \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} s^{n-k} (2k+1) \left\{ \frac{1}{r_k} \sum_{\nu=0}^k p_{k-\nu} q_\nu \right\} \right| \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq \frac{(2n+1)}{2\pi(1+s)^n} \left| \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} s^{n-k} \right|$$

$$= O(n).$$

This proves the lemma.

Lemma-4.2:

$$|K_n(t)| = O\left(\frac{1}{t}\right), \text{ for } \frac{1}{n+1} \leq t \leq \pi.$$

Proof of Lemma-4.2:

For $\frac{1}{n+1} \leq t \leq \pi$, we have by Jordan's lemma, $\sin\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) \geq \frac{t}{\pi}$, $\sin nt \leq 1$.

Then

$$|K_n(t)| = \frac{1}{2\pi(1+s)^n} \left| \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} s^{n-k} \left\{ \frac{1}{r_k} \sum_{\nu=0}^k p_{k-\nu} q_\nu \frac{\sin\left(\nu + \frac{1}{2}\right)t}{\sin \frac{t}{2}} \right\} \right|$$

$$\leq \frac{1}{2\pi(1+s)^n} \left| \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} s^{n-k} \left\{ \frac{1}{r_k} \sum_{\nu=0}^k \frac{\pi p_{k-\nu} q_\nu}{t} \right\} \right|$$

$$= \frac{1}{2(1+s)^n t} \left| \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} s^{n-k} \left\{ \frac{1}{r_k} \sum_{\nu=0}^k p_{k-\nu} q_\nu \right\} \right|$$

$$= \frac{1}{2(1+s)^n t} \left| \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} s^{n-k} \right|$$

$$= O\left(\frac{1}{t}\right).$$

This proves the lemma.

5. Proof of Theorem 3.1:

Using Riemann –Lebesgue theorem, for the n-th partial sum $s_n(f;x)$ of the Fourier series (1.10) of $f(x)$ and following Titchmarsh [16], we have

$$s_n(f;x) - f(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^\pi \phi(t) \frac{\sin\left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right)t}{\sin\left(\frac{t}{2}\right)} dt.$$

Using (1.2), the (N, p_n, q_n) transform of $s_n(f;x)$ is given by

$$t_n - f(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi r_n} \int_0^\pi \varphi(t) \sum_{k=0}^n p_{n-k} q_\nu \frac{\sin\left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right)t}{\sin\left(\frac{t}{2}\right)} dt.$$

Denoting the $(E, q)(N, p, q)$ transform of $s_n(f; x)$ by τ_n , we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|\tau_n - f\| &= \frac{1}{2\pi(1+s)^n} \int_0^\pi \varphi(t) \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} s^{n-k} \left\{ \frac{1}{r_k} \sum_{\nu=0}^k p_{k-\nu} q_\nu \frac{\sin\left(\nu + \frac{1}{2}\right)t}{\sin\frac{t}{2}} \right\} dt \\ &= \int_0^\pi \phi(t) K_n(t) dt \\ &= \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{n+1}} + \int_{\frac{1}{n+1}}^\pi \right\} \phi(t) K_n(t) dt \\ (5.1) \quad &= I_1 + I_2, \text{ say.} \end{aligned}$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned} |I_1| &= \frac{1}{2\pi(1+s)^n} \left| \int_0^{\frac{1}{n+1}} \varphi(t) \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} s^{n-k} \left\{ \frac{1}{r_k} \sum_{\nu=0}^k p_{k-\nu} q_\nu \frac{\sin\left(\nu + \frac{1}{2}\right)t}{\sin\frac{t}{2}} \right\} dt \right| \\ &\leq \left| \int_0^{\frac{1}{n+1}} \phi(t) K_n(t) dt \right| \\ &\leq \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{n+1}} \left| \frac{t \phi(t) \sin^\beta t}{\xi(t)} \right|^l dt \right)^{\frac{1}{l}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{n+1}} \left| \frac{\xi(t) \bar{K}_n(t)}{t \sin^\beta t} \right|^m dt \right)^{\frac{1}{m}}, \text{ where } \frac{1}{l} + \frac{1}{m} = 1, \text{ using} \end{aligned}$$

Hölder's inequality

$$= O(1) \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{n+1}} \left(\frac{\xi(t)}{t^{1+\beta}} \right)^m dt \right)^{\frac{1}{m}}, \text{ using Lemma 4.1 and (3.1.2)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= O\left(\xi\left(\frac{1}{n+1}\right)\right)\left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{n+1}} \frac{dt}{t^{(1+\beta)m}}\right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \\
 &= O\left(\xi\left(\frac{1}{n+1}\right)\right)O\left((n+1)^{-\frac{1}{m}+1+\beta}\right). \\
 (5.2) \quad &= O\left(\xi\left(\frac{1}{n+1}\right)(n+1)^{\beta+\frac{1}{l}}\right).
 \end{aligned}$$

Next

$$|I_2| \leq \left(\int_{\frac{1}{n+1}}^{\pi} \left|\frac{t^{-\delta} \phi(t) \sin^{\beta} t}{\xi(t)}\right|^l dt\right)^{\frac{1}{l}} \left(\int_{\frac{1}{n+1}}^{\pi} \left|\frac{\xi(t) \bar{K}_n(t)}{t^{-\delta} \sin^{\beta} t}\right|^m dt\right)^{\frac{1}{m}},$$

where $\frac{1}{l} + \frac{1}{m} = 1$, using Hölder's inequality

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= O((n+1)^{\delta}) \left(\int_{\frac{1}{n+1}}^{\pi} \left(\frac{\xi(t)}{t^{\beta+1-\delta}}\right)^m dt\right)^{\frac{1}{m}}, \text{ using Lemma 4.2 and (3.1.3)} \\
 &= O((n+1)^{\delta}) \left(\int_{\frac{1}{\pi}}^{n+1} \left(\frac{\xi\left(\frac{1}{y}\right)}{y^{\delta-\beta-1}}\right)^m \frac{dy}{y^2}\right)^{\frac{1}{m}},
 \end{aligned}$$

since $\xi(t)$ is a positive increasing function, so is $\xi(1/y)/(1/y)$. Using second mean value theorem we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= O((n+1)^{1+\delta}) \xi\left(\frac{1}{n+1}\right) \left(\int_{\varepsilon}^{n+1} \frac{dy}{y^{m(\delta-\beta-1)+2}}\right)^{\frac{1}{m}}, \text{ for some } \frac{1}{\pi} \leq \varepsilon \leq n+1 \\
 &= O\left((n+1)^{1+\delta} \xi\left(\frac{1}{n+1}\right)\right) O\left((n+1)^{\beta+1-\delta-\frac{1}{m}}\right) \\
 (5.3) \quad &= O\left((n+1)^{\beta+\frac{1}{l}} \xi\left(\frac{1}{n+1}\right)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Then from (5.2) and (5.3), we have

$$|\tau_n - f(x)| = O\left((n+1)^{\beta+\frac{1}{l}} \xi\left(\frac{1}{n+1}\right)\right), \text{ for } r \geq 1.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \|\tau_n - f(x)\|_r &= \left(\int_0^{2\pi} O \left((n+1)^{\beta+\frac{1}{l}} \xi \left(\frac{1}{n+1} \right) \right)^l dx \right)^{\frac{1}{l}}, \quad l \geq 1. \\ &= O \left((n+1)^{\beta+\frac{1}{l}} \xi \left(\frac{1}{n+1} \right) \right) \left(\int_0^{2\pi} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{l}} \\ &= O \left((n+1)^{\beta+\frac{1}{l}} \xi \left(\frac{1}{n+1} \right) \right). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of the theorem.

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